

THE DEVELOPMENT OF COMMUNICATIVE LANGUAGE
TEACHING IN MEDICAL ENGLISH CLASSE

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ANNOTATION: The present article studies the implementation ways of CLT activities into the classroom. The actuality of this paper is the investigation of some typical CLT activities in the way of development of the speaking skills to provide communication in learning a foreign language in the field of medicine and making EFL classroom more effective teaching environment as facilitator.

Keywords: Communication, English, medical students, practical activities, communicative competence, role play, job interview

АННОТАЦИЯ: В данной статье изучаются способы внедрения CLT-методы в учебный класс. Актуальность данной статьи заключается в исследовании некоторых типичных CLT- деятельность в плане развития навыков говорения для обеспечения коммуникации при изучении иностранного языка в области медицины и в создании более эффективной учебной среды EFL в качестве фасилитатора.

Ключевые слова: Коммуникация, английский язык, студенты-медики, практическая деятельность, коммуникативная компетентность, мотивация, будущие врачи

Introduction: Communicative Language Teaching (or CLT) is a popular approach to any language teaching which emphasizes using language in the same way that it's used in real life. In other words, you put your students in language situations which are as close to real life as possible. With CLT, you give your students language they need to deal with real situations. You place less importance on producing grammatically correct English but more importance on dealing effectively with the situation.

Communicative competence included knowing what to say and how to say it appropriately based on the situation, the participants, and their roles and intentions. Traditional grammatical and vocabulary syllabuses and teaching methods did not include information of this kind. It was assumed that this kind of knowledge would be picked up informally.

Small group work can also be regarded as an important tenet of CLT. Larsen-Freeman (1986) puts forward that activities in a communicative class are commonly carried out by students in small groups. Negotiation of meaning can be accomplished by involving learners in group work in which they can freely interact with each other. Through small group activities, the students are engaged in meaningful and authentic language use rather than in the simply mechanical practice of language patterns.

Brown (2001), in describing the key principles of CLT, offers the following six characteristics:

1. Classroom goals are focused on all of the components (grammatical, discourse, functional, sociolinguistic, and strategic) of communicative competence. Goals therefore must intertwine the organizational aspects of language with the pragmatic.

2. Language techniques are designed to engage learners in the pragmatic, authentic, functional use of language for meaningful purposes. Organizational language forms are not the central focus, but rather aspects of language that enable learner to accomplish those purposes.

3. Fluency and accuracy are seen as complementary principles underlying communicative techniques. At times fluency may have to take on more importance than accuracy in order to keep learners meaningfully engaged in language use.

4. Students in a communicative class ultimately have to use language, productively and receptively, in unrehearsed contexts outside the classroom. Classroom tasks must therefore equip students with the skills necessary for communication in those contexts.

5. Students are given opportunities to focus on their own learning process through an understanding of their own styles of learning and through the development of appropriate strategies for autonomous learning.

6. The role of the teacher is that of facilitator and guide, not an all-knowing bestower of knowledge. Students are therefore encouraged to construct meaning through genuine linguistic interaction with others. (p. 43)

Methods and materials: The range of exercise types and activities compatible with a CLT approach is unlimited, provided that such exercises enable students to attain the communicative objectives of the curriculum and engage learners in communication. Activities entailing pair work, group work are essential for EFL

learners who are rarely exposed to the target language use in their immediate environment. These activities are meaningful. That is to say, they require learners to make meaningful choices when carrying out practice. Some of these activities are:

1. Information-Gap Activities

The notion of information gap is an important concept in CLT. In real communication people normally have a genuine purpose. They seek information they do not have. In order to practice information activities, certain tasks are used. For example, students are divided into A-B pairs, teacher provides students with two set of pictures slightly different from each other, then asks students to compare and explain the differences to each other. (Richards, 2006). Teacher can also provide one group of students with information about an interesting individual, place or event and ask other group to get information from their peers.

2. Jigsaw Activities

Jigsaw activities are based on the principles of information gap. The class is divided into groups and each group has part of the information necessary for completion of an activity. The class must fit the pieces together to complete the whole. Students must use their language resources to communicate meaningfully and, thus, take part in meaningful communication practice.

3. Role-Plays (doctor and patients)

There are certain activities in which students are assigned roles and improvise a scene on exchange based on some given information or clue. In these activities emphasis is laid on pair work and group work.

4. Interviews (Job interviews)

An interview is an oral activity done in pairs, whose main goal is to develop students' interpersonal skills in the TL.

Results: This article is dedicated to studying the use of CLT activities to activate speaking skills in practical medical English lessons. The ability of speaking a foreign language is synonymous with knowing this language, since speech is for them the main means of human communication. Medical students no longer expect their English teachers to follow the traditional approach, which was mainly based on the development of grammatical competence and the use of methodologies that were popular in the past.

Based on this, I have come to the **following conclusion.**

1. The instructor gives each student the same set of questions to ask a partner.
2. Students take turns asking and answering the questions in pairs.

This activity, since it is highly-structured, allows for the instructor to more closely monitor students' responses. It can zone in on one specific aspect of grammar or vocabulary, while still being a primarily communicative activity and giving the students communicative benefits. This is an activity that should be used primarily in the lower levels of language classes, because it will be most beneficial to lower-level speakers.

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